

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTERACTION BETWEEN ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN AND HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

There is now extensive research demonstrating that good architectural design has distinct psychological and physiological benefits that go beyond simply feeling aesthetically pleasing. Architectural design and the connection of its aspects with human psychology have always been the focus of the attention of modern researchers. The basic connection between architectural design and the psychological qualities of a person is quite significant and remains at a certain level very significant for planning a future construction project. The design system in modern urban planning has a special relationship with psychology, not only indirectly, but also in several directions. On the one hand, this successful design has a clear psychological impact on people's condition. On the other hand, the human psyche requires increased task design functions. Enjoying an architectural structure and its internal design allows people to consider themselves happy, and satisfied and receive visual and aesthetic pleasure. All ways by which a person can achieve these feelings are acceptable in modern architecture, taking into account not only the interests of people but also taking into account the available natural conditions and resources.

Keywords: architecture, project, psychology, design, emotions, fashion, convenience, perception, interior, adaptation.

Architecture originated in the Middle Ages and throughout human history has been a means of protecting people from the environment. Over time, it began to develop into a form of so-called art. The visual impact of a building under construction on the human psyche has become one of the important aspects of architecture. A creative approach to any architectural project requires not only beauty but also convenience for future life and human activity [1;4].

Modern architecture is rapidly developing in the modern world and one of the directions of this industry is connected with all forms of contemporary art. The connection between architecture and art is one of the factors ensuring the psychological well-being of people on construction sites. The psychological effects of architectural design and art design are of great importance for the positive emotional and psychological well-being of people [2;5].

Art design in architecture allows you to take into account all the needs of people in improving their homes or offices. Interior design, taking into account the psychological characteristics of human needs in architecture, influences the psychology of people; this is important to take into account at a basic level, where the psychological impact of certain art stimuli on the human psyche is revealed [3;6].

Based on this, it can be stated that the architectural style changes and develops over time, taking into account the desires of the general public and the discovery of more and more new building materials. If we analyze the history of the development of architecture, we can note that what was once fashionable changes over

time, what has existed for centuries loses value, and new trends appear [2;7].

The value of a building that gives us a feeling of satisfaction from its external and internal appearance depends on the architectural elements that our psyche perceives positively. Modern architects must be able to recognize what exactly the human psyche perceives with this building element [8].

Any model or project during construction and design becomes a subject of interest to the consumer, i.e. customer, everyone wants to know more about future adaptation and tries to take part in the planning themselves. The human psyche is aimed at the future and every architectural nuance of a building and its design affects his mental state. The comparison and presentation of all the signs of a future object are analyzed at the neural level of the human nervous system, this is influenced by the person's previous experiences, fantasies, and desires. The perception of the appearance and interior design of a future office, apartment, or house directly affects the human nervous system; a positive perception gives euphoria, and a negative perception reduces catharsis and sublimation. Sometimes our brains become accustomed to patterns, and breaking them allows a person to develop their creativity.

The human psyche must be aware of the feelings that he experiences when encountering a pattern or lack thereof, when planning and constructing any architectural object.

Any architectural plan and drawing of a future object must meet the psychological and emotional requirements of the client. Architecture must create an

aesthetic response in the observer. Many experts consider the entire structure of a project to be architecture as the rhythm of life. This rhythm of the project mustn't disturb the client's life rhythm, but on the contrary, can attract their attention, as well as contribute to their requirements and can embellish their everyday everyday life.

In architectural design, it is necessary to pay attention to four categories of rhythms: sequence, development, perspectives of repetition of a contrasting pair; increasing or decreasing the size of all elements in the project; continuity and repetition of one or another element of the project and design; straight and other lines, elements that allow you to differ from previous projects.

In modern architecture, a new trend associated with the imitation of natural elements (forests, mountains, ponds, etc.) is relevant. An example of such structures is the Sagrada Familia in Barcelona, designed by Antoni Gaudi, where we can find elements branching at the tops and converging in the ceiling and each other, like the intertwining branches of tree canopies. The next project, the Taichung National Theater, located in Taiwan, designed by Toyo Ito, resembles a natural rock formation. The Eden Project in Cornwall, England, consists of several transparent domes housing a wide variety of plants. Architect Nicholas Grimshaw took inspiration from bubbles, allowing the translucent domes to seamlessly coexist with the surrounding nature. Cafe "Pearl" in Baku, symbolizes marine fauna. The architects of the cafe were V Shulgin and R. Sharifov. The next object of admiration in the city of Baku is the modern shopping center "Deniz Mall" designed in the shape of a blooming lotus by Tim Curran, director of the Chapman Taylor company. "Flame Towers" are skyscrapers located in Baku. The towers' appearance resembles three flames, the architect of the project was the HOK company, which was founded in St. Louis, Missouri, the name of the company comes from the names of its three founding partners: George F. Hellmuth, Ge Obata, and George Kassabaum. And another very interesting architectural solution can be seen

in the structure of the sports and concert complex, intended for holding international cultural events, "Baku Crystal Hall", reminiscent of a large crystal. The architect of this modern architectural masterpiece was Alpine Bau Deutschland AG. All these buildings are known for their beauty all over the world.

One of the main reasons we perceive these buildings as beautiful is because our brain processes the sensory information it receives from them and relates it to patterns that have previously proven their evolutionary usefulness in nature. However, because this pattern recognition occurs at a subconscious level, most viewers are unaware of the neuropsychological and physiological basis for perceiving this sense of beauty. The same physiological response can occur even if the building's resemblance to its surroundings is not as obvious as in the examples above.

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